

SEASONAL CHANGES AS IT AFFECTS THE INCIDENCE OF VIRAL AND FUNGAL DISEASES OF TOMATO

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ABSTRACT

The experiment was carried out at the National Horticultural Research Institute, Ibadan, Nigeria during the 2009 and 2010 cropping season to examine the incidence of common fungal and viral diseases affecting tomato crop during the rainy and dry season. The experimental design was a Randomised Complete Block Design with four replications. During the rainy season, tomato seeds were sown in the nursery in May and the seedlings transplanted to the field 4 weeks after sowing and during the dry season, tomato seeds were sown in December 2009 and transplanted 4 weeks after sowing. The incidence of fungi, virus or mixed fungi and virus diseases was recorded fortnightly starting from 2 to 10 weeks after transplanting in each season. In both the rainy and dry seasons, the incidence of mixed virus and fungi diseases was low during the early growth stage and increased as the plant developed. The most prevalent type of disease during the rainy and dry seasons was the viral disease. The diseased plants showed significant reduction in all the growth and yield attributes examined but there was no significant difference between the early infected and the late infected plant in the growth and yield attributes except for the plant height and the fruit weight. However, the healthy plant had a significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) growth and yield attributes compared with those with early and late disease infection.

KEYWORDS: Tomato, disease incidence, rainy and dry seasons, early and late infections.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) belongs to the family *Solanaceae*. World tomato production in 2001 was about 105 million tons of fresh fruits from an estimated 3.9 million hectares (FAOSTAT, 2007). Tomato fruit contains lots of minerals and vitamins which are parts of essential human food nutrients required for proper growth and development. Lycopene is an important antioxidant present in ripe red tomato fruit which has some anticancer property (Ibitoye *et al.*, 2009). It has been grown in various parts of Nigeria for long time as evidenced by the occurrence of various local varieties.

Tomatoes are often affected by a number of pests and diseases. Most diseases of tomato are caused by various fungi, bacteria, viruses and nematodes. Fungi and bacteria cause foliar, stem, root, and fruit diseases (Adebayo, 2005). A virus infection often leads to dwarf growth and reduced production. Diseases generally result in considerable tomato fruit yield losses for a farmer. Seasonal climatic change is one of the key factors that influence disease infection, because if the climatic conditions are not made favourable for the harmful micro-organisms, pathogen infection on tomato plant may not be established. The frequency of successful inoculation of pathogen depends on the amount of inoculum available, occurrence of suitable temperature and moisture which favour release of inocula, germination of spore, and activity of its vectors, the direction of air currents or windblown rain (Agrios, 1988).

Therefore, efficiency of infection in Host-Pathogen interaction, symptoms development and yield responses of host plant is greatly influenced by environmental conditions like temperature and light variations, season of the year, nutrition and water supply.

Pathogenic infections in some instances are transmitted through insects feeding on tomato plant especially those feeding on plant cell sap (like aphids, whitefly, thrips, mites) (Wittwer, 1998). Pathogens may be soil-borne, air borne, rain splashed or on bear ground plants (Villareal, 1992).

Major tomato diseases that attack the root system of tomatoes are (*Fusarium* wilt, *Verticillium* wilt, bacterial wilt, nematodes, *Rhizoctonia*); the-ground stems and foliage are attacked by causal agent (early blight, septoria leaf spot, bacterial canker, late blight), and fruit (bacterial spot, bacterial speck, anthracnose).The most important viral diseases of tomatoes in Nigeria include tomato bunchy top virus (TBTv), tomato yellows and tomato mosaic virus (ToMV) (Lana and Adegbola, 1977). Plants infected with viral diseases should be rouged to prevent spread of the diseases.

This work was embarked upon to determine the percentage incidence of various tomato diseases at different planting seasons and to determine the effect of early and late infection on the growth and yield of tomato.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at the research farm of National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Ibadan (N 07.40325, E 003.85059, 174 m) during the 2009 and 2010 cropping seasons. The tomato plants were grown on the field between June and October 2009 and December 2009 and April 2010

The experimental design was a randomised complete block with four replicates. In both seasons, beds were made manually with hoe after ploughing and harrowing with tractor-driven equipment. The seedlings were transplanted into 18 beds each measuring 2m x 2m. Seedlings of tomato var. (Roma) were raised in the nursery for 4 weeks before transplanting to the main beds at a spacing of 50cm x50cm and a total of 25 plants per bed. During the dry season, the plants were watered thrice a week, using watering can throughout the duration of the trial. NPK (15:15:15) fertilizer was applied at the rate of 120 kg per hectare two weeks after transplant during both trials. Weeding was done manually, and staking was done when necessary.

In both trials, the diseases were grouped into three categories namely: virus only, fungi only and mixed fungi and virus infection which were also treatments under the different seasons. The percentage incidence of each category of disease per bed was determined using the formula below (Adebayo, 2005)

$$\frac{\text{Number of infected plants / bed}}{\text{Population of plants / bed}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Characteristic symptoms were used to identify the category of pathogenic diseases and the actual numbers of plants infected per bed was recorded as either virus alone, fungi alone or fungi and virus infected plants. Plants that showed infection early (vegetative stage) and late (and flowering stage) were also tagged for data collection to assess the effect of time of infection on some attributes of the plant. Stem girth was measured by venier calliper, the height was measured with the use of a tape rule, while number of leaves of apparently healthy and visibly diseased plants was counted directly. Data were collected bi-weekly on the types of disease that were prevalent during the different seasons. All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance and treatment difference separated using Standard Error or Least Significance Difference.

Isolation and Identification of fungi

Fungi infected plant samples were collected from the field .They were washed with tap water .The infected parts were cut into small pieces and then surface sterilized in 70% ethanol before rinsing in three changes of sterile distilled water and blotted dry with sterile filter paper .The cut surface-sterilised infected plant parts were then aseptically plated on sterilised Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. The plates were incubated at 28±2°C for five days .Sub-culturing was done until pure cultures of the isolates were obtained and maintained on PDA slants in MacCartney bottles .The identification up to generic level was carried out using both colony morphology and microscopic characteristics (Jones *et al.*, 1991).

RESULTS

The isolated fungi were identified as *Fusarium* spp. causing wilt, *Alternaria* sp. causing leaf blight, *Septoria* sp. causing septoria leaf spot. The leaf curl disease was identified with the symptoms of twisted leaves and cessation of growth of the terminal ends while the mosaic virus disease was identified by the characteristic symptom of light and dark green areas on the infected leaves.

Percentage disease incidence followed the same trend during the rainy and dry seasons. The percentage disease incidence of each disease (that is fungal and viral) and the mixed infections of both fungal and viral infections

were low at the early stage of growth but increased as the tomato plants developed (Tables 1 and 2). However, there was higher percentage of disease incidence recorded in the rainy season than that of the dry season .The most prevalent type of disease during the rainy and dry seasons was the viral infection.

During the rainy season, there was a significant difference in the percentage incidence of fungal, viral and mixed fungal and viral infections with viral infection being the most prevalent from 2WAT to 10 WAT, though there was no significant difference between fungal (2.12) and mixed (1.13) infections at 2 WAT; but from 4 to 8 WAT, there was significant difference in percentage of disease incidence. At 10 WAT, there was no significant difference in percentage incidence of viral (28.60) and mixed infection (29.80) (Table 1).

Results of dry season planting show that at 2, 4 and 6 WAT, there was no significant difference in the percentage incidence of the various diseases (Table 2) while at 8 and 10 WAT, a significant difference was observed for viral infection while no significant difference was observed between the fungal and mixed infection (Table2) .

Tables 3 and 4 shows significant differences between healthy and diseased plants in favour of the former in growth and yield attributes during both the rainy and dry seasons. Yield was observed to be higher in the rainy season than in the dry season despite the higher percentage disease incidence of the raining season.

A significant difference in plant height and fruit weight was noticed between the early and late infected tomato plant. Healthy plant had a significantly higher growth and yield attributes compared with both early and late diseased plants (Table5).

DISCUSSION

Fusarium sp., *Alternaria* sp., and *Septoria* sp. are common fungal pathogens of tomato (Adebayo, 2005; Akhtar *et al.*, 2004; Mensah *et al.*, 2009; Gleason and Edmunds, 2006).The incidence of viral leaf curl and mosaic infection on tomato plant had been reported by Arogundade *et al.* (2007). Higher incidence of tomato diseases during the rainy season than during the dry season corroborated the findings of Mensah *et al.* (2004). This could be attributed to the wet and warm climatic conditions during the rainy season which favour the dissemination and growth of the pathogens. Heavy rains and high humidity increase the occurrence of insect pests and diseases. When tomato plants grow in contact with wet soil, the humidity under the plants increases, and in turn increases pests and diseases menace (Gerber, 1979). The fungal pathogens identified with tomato disease in this study are largely soil – borne.

During the dry season, tomato plants wilt and flowers drop due to continuous hot weather and this is one of the reasons for higher yield parameter observed in the rainy season than in the dry season despite the higher percentage disease incidence observed in the raining season.

Disease is a factor that prevents crops from achieving their genetic potentials. This was reflected in the lower growth and yield attributes of the diseased plant than the healthy one.

CONCLUSION

Tomato plant grown in the rainy season had better growth and yield attributes than that of dry season. Also growing the crop in dry season requires more fund (in terms of irrigation) and energy. If good agricultural practices, like crop rotation , staking ,using clean farm implements ,application of bio -control methods etc. can be practiced, then it will help to reduce pests and diseases problems of tomato plant even during rainy season.

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Table 1: Percentage incidence of diseases over a 10 week period after transplanting during rainy season

Treatment	2 WAT	4 WAT	6 WAT	8 WAT	10 WAT
Fungus alone	2.12	1.78	2.13	5.7	10.59
Virus alone	13.81	22.72	30.11	29.6	28.60
Fungus + virus	1.13	2.71	5.42	12.43	29.80
Standard Error	0.54	0.69	0.97	1.55	1.27

Table 2: Percentage incidence of diseases over a 10 week period after transplanting during dry season

Treatment	2 WAT	4 WAT	6 WAT	8 WAT	10 WAT
Fungus alone	0.00	1.67	1.67	3.52	5.19
Virus alone	1.67	2.65	8.15	11.67	13.34
Fungus + virus	0.00	3.33	3.33	3.70	6.35
Standard Error	0.67	1.76	3.11	1.79	2.20

Table 3: Effect of health status of a tomato plant on the growth and yield attributes at 6 WAT during the rainy season

Health status	Plant height (cm)	Number of leaves	Number of branches	Stem girth (cm)	Total number of flowers
Diseased plant	50.00	30.00	5.33	0.88	3.00
Healthy plant	106.00	92.33	9.67	1.62	55.33
LSD.(P<0.05)	47.25	16.61	3.46	0.34	23.74

Table 4: Effect of health status of a tomato plant on the growth and yield attributes at 6 WAT during the dry season

Health status	Plant height (cm)	Number of leaves/plant	Number of branches	Stem girth (cm)	Total number of flowers
Diseased plant	46.21	26.01	4.21	0.81	3.00
Healthy plant	68.82	56.32	7.92	1.52	51.24
LSD(P<0.05)	15.14	10.41	2.35	0.29	21.19

Table 5: Effect of time of infection on the growth and yield attributes of Tomato during the dry season

Time of infection(n)	Plant Height (cm)	Number of leaves/plant	Number of branches	Stem girth (cm)	Number of flowers	Number of fruits/plant	Weight of fruits (g)/plant
Early infection	40.33	28.33	2.33	0.87	5.33	2.00	10.13
Late infection	70.00	51.00	4.00	1.11	14.00	6.00	47.23
Healthy	109.00	97.00	10.33	1.46	56.33	16.67	99.67
LSD (P<0.05)	10.19	22.19	5.49	0.32	19.26	6.95	31.66

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